

Innovation of Rural Tourism Marketing Strategy in the Internet Environment

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Abstract: With the continuous development of information technology, the Internet is loved by all walks of life for its intelligent, convenient and efficient characteristics.

At present, under the continuous promotion of the national rural revitalization strategy, farmers' incomes are increasing, living standards are constantly improving, and rural tourism is also developing. Therefore, it is of great significance to create a unique rural tourism culture and promote the development and marketing strategy of rural tourism. This paper mainly takes the Internet environment as the background and rural tourism marketing as the research object, and puts forward corresponding suggestions for the current problems and current situation in rural tourism marketing. In order to provide ideas and suggestions for the future development of rural tourism marketing in China.

Keywords: Rural Tourism; Tourism Marketing; Internet; Marketing Countermeasures

I. INTRODUCTION

At present, the continuous development and growth of Internet technology, the continuous popularization of information technology, and people's living standards are also improving day by day. In recent years, with the continuous improvement of China's economic level, tourism has gradually developed and expanded. However, for rural tourism, most areas still use traditional marketing methods, such as TV advertisements and real radio advertisements. Traditional marketing methods are no longer suitable for the current new trend of mass tourism, which has led to the stagnation of tourism in some rural areas, which largely restricts the development of rural tourism. Rural tourism can allow more audiences to feel the natural atmosphere different from the city, different from the city's rural experience, etc., representing the current tourism values of the public. Therefore, the development of rural tourism has a unique value advantage. Based on this, under the new Internet ecology, how to better use new technologies to attract tourists, promote rural economic development, and effectively promote the development of rural tourism is a key step.

II. MARKETING STATUS OF RURAL TOURISM IN THE INTERNET ENVIRONMENT

As an emerging type of tourism, rural tourism is different from the traditional way of checking in at famous scenic spots, rural tourism can give full play to the advantages of the countryside itself, and create unique tourism projects in a natural, local and life-oriented way, so that tourists can have attraction and influence. The innovation of rural tourism marketing strategy is to improve the attractiveness of tourism resources to tourists, some scholars pointed out that rural tourism is to go to the agricultural environment, watch the agricultural landscape, engage in agricultural activities, through viewing Investigate, experience, participate, etc., in the form of relaxation. Therefore, rural tourism marketing is of great significance to promote rural economic development, improve the employment rate of rural farmers and increase the visibility of rural areas.

Different from the traditional rural tourism model, the current rural tourism model has undergone tremendous changes, no longer limited to the traditional form of farmhouse, but has a more variety of expressions. Rural parks, animal breeding science popularization, cultural and creative parks and other forms, and constantly to customize The direction of leisure has changed. Although there are many benefits of rural tourism, due to the weak marketing ability and strength of rural tourism, some adjustments need to be made at present to let more audiences understand and have better development in the future.

At present, China is in an information age, all kinds of information technology emerge endlessly, and with the people's daily life is inextricably linked, especially the mobile Internet, it has become an irreplaceable part of people's daily life. If rural tourism wants to occupy a place in this wide variation, the key is innovation, not only to innovate marketing methods, but also to take the initiative to change the mode of thinking, combined with the current cutting-edge information technology, only according to the characteristics of the village itself, to develop a strategy that can be consistent with the direction of rural development, can rural tourism in the new Internet environment Achieving better development can also promote better development in China's tourism marketing field.

III. THE NECESSITY OF INNOVATION IN RURAL TOURISM MARKETING STRATEGIES

A. BUILD a Rural Brand Image and Enhance Market Competitiveness

At present, due to the extensive use of Internet technology, it provides great convenience for public life. In this context, mobile Internet plays an important role in rural tourism marketing, sharing good mountains, good water and good scenery in rural areas with the public through the network, promoting the development of rural tourism, and enhancing the competitiveness and influence of regional tourism industries. In recent years, the national level has also begun to pay close attention to the development of the Internet, and clearly put forward the development strategy of "Internet +" and rural revitalization ^[1]. Therefore, in the general environment of the Internet, if we want to better develop the countryside, we should conform to the general trend of the times and consciously and actively change our thinking. Broaden the consumer group of rural tourism, establish rural tourism brand awareness, and innovate marketing strategies. According to the village's own customs and habits, a series of tourism products with local characteristics can be created, or starting from experiential marketing that consumers are interested in, according to the needs of the public. Set up new scenes with rural characteristics, further enhance market competitiveness and other practical needs, and strive to build a brand rural tourism industry with local characteristics.

B. Realize the Integration of Rural Tourism and the Internet and promote the Development of Related Economic Industries

With the proposal of the rural revitalization strategy, the continuous improvement of the rural industrial structure, and the rapid development of the Internet today, people's lifestyles have changed, and the state attaches importance to rural tourism, for the Internet environment rural tourism marketing has brought new development opportunities and space, and laid a good foundation for the integration of the two. In recent years, although some villages have benefited from the promulgation of the policy, due to the failure to establish a long-term brand service awareness, tourists have a poor sense of experience after coming and have not formed a good reputation. This requires rural tourism operators to use Internet technology on the one hand to release relevant information, attract tourists, and enhance the popularity and exposure of rural areas. On the other hand, it is also necessary to obtain advanced marketing knowledge from the Internet to lay a foundation for subsequent innovative marketing models and promote industrial development. Through the deep integration of rural tourism and Internet technology, it can effectively accelerate the development of rural tourism, innovate marketing strategies, attract consumers to actively participate in rural life, and bring economic support for the subsequent better development of rural tourism.

C. Give Play to the Influence of the Internet Marketing methods to stimulate netizens to carry out rural tourism

From the perspective of rural tourism, the typical characteristics reflected in the whole process of rural tourism project development and marketing of rural tourism products are that it has the characteristics of intangibility and remoteness ^[2]. For people in the city, rural tourism can well meet the needs of the masses. The mobile Internet has the characteristics of strong information integration ability and large industrial integration ability. If we want to better use the power of the Internet, we must make moderate innovation in the marketing model of rural tourism and make differences, so as to attract more interested tourists to experience rural life, thereby stimulating the growth of rural tourism economy, promoting the employment of farmers, and promoting the prosperity of rural economy. Through Internet marketing, on the one hand, it can ensure that consumers experience more humane and specialized services for experiential and reservation-based services, and provide consumers with a comfortable and distinctive rural experience; On the other hand, you can also show the real rural life to the public by publishing graphic information to the Internet platform, and present the bits and pieces of daily life to the audience of the Internet platform. So as to enhance tourists, especially tourists in the city, yearning for a pleasant life in the countryside, and further better stimulate the public to carry out rural tourism and build beautiful countryside.

IV. THE PROBLEMS OF RURAL TOURISM MARKETING STRATEGY UNDER THE BACKGROUND OF THE INTERNET

A. Project Managers have Insufficient Understanding of Internet Marketing

At present, the development of rural tourism has made rapid progress. However, at present, many rural tourism project managers have not realized the great technical, cost and resource advantages of Internet marketing, and the marketing thinking of some managers has not changed, and they are still stuck in the previous marketing stage, which cannot effectively enhance the popularity of local tourism projects. Therefore, the marketing model of rural tourism is still in a relatively traditional stage and the marketing concept is relatively backward, which cannot effectively play the advantages of the Internet, making it difficult to organically combine with the rural tourism economy ^[3]. At the same time, because managers have not yet done in-depth mining and development of specific rural tourism resources, they have been copying other regional tourism marketing models, resulting in the homogenization of rural tourism. Internet technology and rural tourism marketing have not been deeply integrated, the advantages of Internet marketing have not been brought into play, and the relevant technical chains and service standards are still in place. This has led to major problems in the long-term sustainable development of some rural tourism, which is difficult to carry out for a long time, and the impact on the local economy is also huge.

B. Lack of Professional Rural Tourism Internet Marketing Team

The development of rural tourism is directly related to the professionalism and marketing ability of its rural tourism marketing team. The marketing team will directly affect the subsequent development and construction of rural tourism. At present, the marketing strategies and marketing concepts of some rural tourism in China are still in a relatively traditional stage, which leads to a relatively single source of tourists for rural tourism, and the connection of tourism resources is not in place. At present, it is a common phenomenon that the rural tourism network marketing team is less professional, so although many rural tourism places have completed the purchase of relevant equipment, due to the current lack of professional talents in rural tourism marketing, the marketing results are not satisfactory. The marketing team cannot stand on a professional standpoint, use Internet technology to carry out the planning and marketing of tourism products, and cannot use Internet technology to timely and effectively statistically analyze and release relevant information resources, so that the technical advantages of the Internet cannot be fully exerted in the marketing of rural tourism. At present, the marketing method of rural tourism marketing team using the Internet is only manifested in publishing basic information on relevant platforms, and does not use big data, artificial intelligence and other technologies to deeply analyze and describe tourist portraits, and cannot directly translate current technical capabilities into marketing results. This directly reflects the current lack of excellent marketing talents, which is also the biggest gap between rural tourist attractions and urban tourism projects.

C. The Market Division is not Clear, and the Marketing Lacks Pertinence

For rural tourism, tourist needs are becoming increasingly diverse, and there are great differences in the access to tourism information and the demand for rural tourism among tourist groups of different ages. Therefore, it is necessary to implement personalized marketing strategies for different age groups to improve competitiveness. In the Internet era, big data plays an increasingly important role, and rural tourism marketing activities based on the collection and analysis of big data can make marketing more accurate and efficient. Some rural areas lack unified management of tourism resources and facilities, each rural tourist attraction has its own way, and most of them adopt the past business model, can not take the initiative, always passively wait for the choice of tourists, the daily operation of various data that can reflect the needs and intentions of tourists, etc., are not effectively collected, which leads to the inability to accurately count the needs and ideas of tourists who come to rural tourism. These problems directly affect the formulation of subsequent rural marketing strategies. In the process of rural tourism, due to the lack of big data support, so in the sales process can not be provided according to the needs of different customer groups, just through the traditional push channel, the same service information is boldly pushed to everyone, such a marketing method lacks targeting. In the end, the marketing effect of

rural tourism is not satisfactory and the return on investment is low.

V. THE INNOVATION OF RURAL TOURISM MARKETING STRATEGY

A. Promote the Transformation of Managers' Cognitive Concepts and Realize Smart Marketing

Under the background of the Internet, to promote the continuous innovation of rural tourism marketing strategies, the most important thing is to fully explore and show the rural characteristics through marketing according to the characteristics of the countryside itself. This requires managers to fully explore the culture and characteristics of the countryside, which can be presented by reading local history or local history, and then using modern scientific and technological means to promote the sustainable development of rural tourism. First of all, it is necessary to train managers in certain rural cultural knowledge, so that managers have a certain understanding of rural tourism, and secondly, it is necessary to actively create a "smart marketing" model. The marketing model is becoming more and more diversified and informatized, and at the same time can apply a variety of mobile Internet-related resources, relying on new communication technology, sharing rural tourism content, and promoting the rapid dissemination of information, so as to ensure that consumers can bring better tourism information and personalized services. Finally, the project manager in charge of rural tourism should not only learn the local history and culture, but also strengthen the learning of advanced technology. In order to effectively combine the advantages of local resources, provide diversified and effective marketing channels, and vigorously develop rural tourism with characteristics, so that rural tourism projects under the leadership of managers, form projects with local characteristics and innovative marketing models, so as to promote the rapid development of rural tourism economy and enhance the market competitiveness of rural tourism.

B. Increase the Introduction of Talents and Improve Demand-Oriented Innovation

To realize the innovation of rural tourism, it is necessary to abandon the shackles of single and ineffective network marketing in the traditional concept, accurately grasp the operation law of the market, rationally change the concept, and reasonably innovate marketing strategies. Only in this way can we truly realize the innovation of traditional marketing ideas and keep pace with the times. In the context of the Internet, it is necessary to follow the trend of the development of the times, attach importance to the introduction and training of talents, accurately position the market, and form a demand-oriented rural tourism marketing model. The innovation of rural tourism marketing strategy should stand in the perspective of consumers, establish a professional marketing team with the help of Internet technology, accurately locate rural tourism projects, and build rural local resources. First of all, before formulating marketing strategies, it is necessary to do relevant market research work, especially for customers with potential consumer demand, and then, on this basis, create word-of-mouth, experience, ritual or comprehensive marketing paths

The model of "combination punch" is a new idea of Internet marketing. Finally, it is necessary to establish a marketing team according to local needs, pay attention to the introduction and training of talents, and improve rural infrastructure construction, such as road traffic and public toilets and entertainment activities, etc., to create characteristic and humanized tourism projects to attract and retain more tourists.

C. Establish Marketing Databases and Implement Precision Marketing

Big data marketing is to use the Internet to obtain a large amount of relevant data, and then use computer high-speed computing to identify information with use value in order to sell in a targeted manner. The core of big data marketing is to make online advertising suitable for itself through the appropriate carrier and appropriate method. Through the construction of a database of rural tourism tourists' needs, it provides basic information for the development of rural tourism network marketing activities more intelligently, and uses these information as a reference and basis for the development of subsequent projects. Through the collection of the Internet, the portrait of tourists is analyzed, and through the analysis, the needs of tourists in this place can be seen, and corresponding services can be formulated. Subsequently, according to these data, the tourists' tourism motivation, consumption capacity, travel time, travel methods, etc. can be analyzed in detail, and then relevant tourism products can be formulated according to the relevant situation of tourists. Fully prepare for another tour of the tourists. This kind of data to establish a marketing database, to identify the target market, describe the tourist portrait, implement market segmentation, design and develop related projects, not only can fully meet the needs of different types of tourists tourism products, but also can be based on this, targeted Different audiences, personalized marketing. At the same time, it is also necessary to develop tourism projects with its own characteristics according to local conditions, and constantly innovate marketing channels, such as setting up websites, WeChat public account, Douyin account, Xiaohongshu and other media platforms to build a perfect marketing system.

VI. CONCLUSION

In the current environment of the continuous development of the Internet, promoting the innovation of China's rural tourism marketing model not only promotes local economic development, but also has certain benefits for cultural dissemination. Therefore, this paper takes rural tourism as the research object, analyzes its current situation and existing problems, and puts forward specific marketing strategies. It is expected to put forward certain suggestions for the prosperity and development of rural tourism, which is one of the important ways to improve the employment rate of rural areas, promote economic development, and effectively spread rural culture, which can not only bring huge economic benefits to local residents, but also in the can promote rural economic development. At present, through the help of Internet platforms, innovative marketing strategies for rural tourism are of great significance to the

implementation of rural revitalization strategies and the promotion of urban-rural integration.

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